

The Influence of Parental Attention and Interest in Learning on Students' Economics Learning Achievement Class X Pematang Siantar 3 Public High School

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ABSTRACT

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The variables in this research are parental achievement and interest in learning as independent variables and learning achievement as the dependent variable. This type of research is quantitative research with an *E-xpost Facto approach*, with a research population of class X students at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar and a research sample of class Data collection techniques used instruments: (1) parental attention questionnaire, (2) learning interest questionnaire, and (3) learning achievement questionnaire. The results of this research show that: (1) there is a positive and significant influence of learning facilities on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of parental attention (5.299) > t table value (1.65462) which means the variable is significant. (2) there is a positive and significant influence of interest in learning on learning achievement (5.095) > t table value (1.65462) which means this variable is significant. (3) Parental attention and interest in learning together influence learning achievement, this result can be seen in the F test where the calculated F value (17.485) is > compared to the F table value (2.66). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.185, meaning that 18.5% of the variables of parental attention and interest in learning had an influence on student learning achievement at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar and the remaining 81.5% was the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

INTRODUCTION

Parental attention to children is found in the context of guidance in the family. This was stated by Suharsana in I Wayan Djiwa (2008: 1-7), who stated that parental guidance consists of: attention, advice, promises and appreciation. Attention outside of school. Parents who are very attentive influence children's success in the learning process, because after all parental attention is very important in caring for and paying attention to children. The nature of parents and family management can have a positive or negative impact on children's learning. Parental involvement is a supporting factor for student learning both at home and at school. Habits adopted by parents who mismanage the family can have a bad influence on children. In this case, the child not only does not want to learn, but tends to be naughty.

Not only parental attention, interest is an important factor in student learning success. Interest is a person's desire or interest in something. High interest can motivate someone to learn and develop abilities in that field. Conversely, low interest can make someone less motivated and reluctant to learn. In learning, attention is needed to be able to understand what is being learned. By increasing students' interest in learning, the learning process can take the form of activities, where students work and experience what is in their environment individually or in groups. Interest in learning has a very big influence on academic success, because if you study without interest, then students will not study well because it is not interesting to them.

Learning achievement can be influenced by parental attention and good interest in learning. According to Dakri, attention is the activity of increasing awareness of all the functions of the soul which are mobilized to focus attention on something both inside and outside. So, someone who has attention and good relationships (not *broken home*) tends to have a greater capacity to adapt to the environment, solve problems quickly and accurately, even within the range of optimal performance.

Children who experience *broken homes* also study at school. Family background can certainly be an obstacle to academics at school. Children who experience *a broken home* will feel inferior to their friends because their parents are experiencing many problems such as. Problems that *broken-home* children often experience at school are being lazy about studying, skipping school, often fighting teachers, poor self-adjustment, liking to be alone, and being aggressive. So, if students have divorced parents, they must pay attention to the child's interest in learning, because it has an impact on learning activities, if learning activities are disrupted it will affect learning achievement in both negative and positive directions.

Based on observations made at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar there are still students whose interest in learning is low. Parental attention can still be said to be low. This can be seen from the interest of students who are lazy about doing homework, often do not attend school, do not pay attention to the teacher explaining the material, prefer to talk to their classmates and rarely take notes on the material given by the teacher. This is caused by a lack of support and

motivation from parents, causing students' interest in learning to be low and affecting student learning achievement, so encouragement from parents and motivation is needed in order to foster students' interest in learning. Low parental attention can be seen from parents who pay less attention to their children's learning, which causes difficulties in the learning process. Some children have good learning abilities, but because their learning style is irregular, children experience difficulties in these subjects. Therefore, learning results that are less than optimal can cause unsatisfactory learning achievements. Parents who pay less attention to their children's appearance (neatness of uniforms and cleanliness) can affect their children's learning at school.

Meanwhile, in the odd semester exam, the economics subject teacher with a KKM of 72 hopes that 95% of students will succeed in achieving a score above the KKM in the odd semester exam in economics subjects, but in reality, seen from the odd semester exam score table, there are still students who fail the economics exam. , only 64 students or 45% of students completed the economics subject exam and 81 or 55% of students did not complete it.

Based on the description above, the author is interested in conducting research with the title: "The Influence of Parental Attention and Students' Interest in Learning on The Economic Learning Achievement of Class X Students of SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar T.A 2022/2023".

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. Parents attention

Attention is psychic concentration, a psychological aspect that is directed at one object that comes from within and outside the individual. Parental attention is the tendency or active attention of parents who are mobilized to provide encouragement or motivation to be positive to their children to achieve optimal learning. According to Sumanto (2014: 160), attention is mental activity directed towards a particular object and the element of thinking has the strongest influence. According to Nasution (2008:1), it is said that parents are anyone who is responsible for a family or household duties, in daily life as father and mother.

2. Interest in Learning

Interest in learning is a conscious effort made to change behavior, both in the areas of knowledge, attitudes and skills. According to Djaali (2013:21), he says that interest can be expressed through statements that show that students prefer one thing over another, it can also be manifested through participation in an activity.

3. Learning outcomes

Learning achievement is the result of learning that has taken part in an educational program which is made into grades. Nana Sudjana (2004:111), learning achievement is the learning results achieved by students with certain criteria. Meanwhile, according to Dd Mudjiono (2005:3), learning achievement

is the result of an interaction between acts of learning and acts of teaching. Based on this statement, it is known that learning achievement is the result of the learning and teaching process.

METHODS

This research uses a quantitative type of research using the *E-xpost Facto approach*. According to Sugiyono (2010:11), *Ex-post Facto* research uses a correlational approach, namely research to determine the relationship between two or more variables. This researcher used a correlation approach with the aim of finding out the relationship between two variables, namely Parental Attention (X1) and Learning Interest (X2) on Student Learning Achievement (Y).

Based on the researcher's title "The Influence of Parental Attention and Interest in Learning on the Economics Learning Achievement of Class X Students of SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar. This research was carried out at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar in August - September 20 23. The population in this study was class X SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar, totaling 1 57 students. The sample in this study was all students from the population taken, namely all class X students of SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar, totaling 1,57 students .

RESULTS

Instrument Validity and Reliability Test Results

After testing the instrument, the researcher then tabulated the results of the respondents' answers by arranging answer codes according to the classification of answers in table form. Tabulation of respondents' answers was carried out with the help of the *Microsoft Excel program* and using analytical data using analytical data in the *SPSS 24 program*. From the results of the calculations carried out you can determine whether or not the statement items in the research instrument are valid.

The statement item is declared valid if the $\text{calculated } r \text{ value} \geq r \text{ table}$ with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. From the results of the validity test, it can be seen that the correlation between each question item and the total score of $n = 30$ shows that the $r \text{ table}$ is 0.361. This means that if the correlation value is more than 0.361 then the question is considered valid. The statement items that will be used when testing the hypothesis are only valid statement items, while invalid items cannot be used in research.

The instrument reliability test is carried out if all research instruments have been tested for validity. The instrument reliability test is carried out to determine the level of confidence in the research instrument used as a tool for collecting data. To calculate the reliability test of the research instrument, the Cronbach alpha formula is used . The instrument is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha coefficient > 0.6 .

Instrument Validity Test

Calculation of the validity of the parental attention questionnaire consisting of 15 statement items, the interest in learning questionnaire consisting of 14 statement items, the learning achievement questionnaire consisting of 15 statement items which were carried out by automatic calculation using data analysis from the *SPSS 24 program*. After testing and statistical analysis.

Items that are declared valid are items that have a correlation value (r) > 0.361 , while items that have a correlation value (r) > 0.361 are valid questionnaire items. This can be concluded that for the parental attention questionnaire (X_1) it is known that there are 15 items in the questionnaire which have a correlation value (r) > 0.361 as many as 13 valid questionnaire items, for the learning motivation questionnaire (X_2) it is known that the questionnaire consists of 14 items which have a correlation value (r) > 0.361 as many as 14 valid questionnaire items or all valid questionnaires, and for the learning achievement questionnaire (Y) it is known that the questionnaire contains 15 items which have a correlation value (r) > 0.361 as many as 13 valid questionnaire items. So the questionnaire used in this research is a valid statement. Where in this research 40 questionnaire items were used in this research.

Instrument Reliability Test

For the questionnaire reliability criteria, if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with a significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$) then the questionnaire is said to be reliable. However, if $r_{count} \leq r_{table}$ then the questionnaire is considered to have no reliability. If the *Cronbach Alpha value* is > 0.60 it is said to be reliable, but if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 it is said to be unreliable.

Cronbach Alpha > 0.60 is declared reliable, and if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 then it is declared unreliable. From the data obtained, it is known that the *Cronbach Alpha* obtained was $0.808 > 0.60$. From the results of calculating the reliability of Parental Attention, it can be concluded that the research instrument (X1) in the research questionnaire used is reliable. If the *Cronbach Alpha value* is > 0.60 then it is declared reliable, and if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 then it is declared unreliable. From the data obtained, it is known that the *Cronbach Alpha* obtained was $0.894 > 0.60$. From the results of calculating the reliability of Interest in Learning, it can be concluded that the research instrument (X2) in the research questionnaire used is reliable. If the *Cronbach Alpha value* is > 0.60 then it is declared reliable, and if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 then it is declared unreliable. From the data obtained, it is known that the *Cronbach Alpha* obtained was $0.839 > 0.60$. From the results of calculating the reliability of Learning Achievement, it can be concluded that the research instrument (Y) in the research questionnaire used is reliable.

Data Normality Test

Figure 1. Normal Probability P-Plot Curve

The results of the p-plot graph test show that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the diagonal direction, which states that the data meets the assumption of normality and the data is declared to be normally distributed. This can be seen in figure 1 above.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 1. Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	Parents attention	.701	1.426 _
	Interest in Learning	.701	1.426 _
a. Dependent Variable: Learning Achievement			

The assumption of *Tolerance* and *Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)* can be stated that if $VIF > 10$ and *Tolerance* value < 0.10 then multicollinearity occurs, and if $VIF < 10$ and *Tolerance* value > 0.10 then multicollinearity does not occur. Based on table 1, it is known that the VIF value of the learning discipline and learning environment variables is $1.426 < 10$ and the *Tolerance* value is $0.701 > 0.10$, so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity in the data .

Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 2 Scatterplot curve

Based on Figure 4.3, it can be seen that the points are spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. Thus it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur.

Multiple Regression Analysis Test

The purpose of the multiple regression analysis test is to determine the direction and how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable.

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Next, the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable is tested with a confidence interval of 95% or $\alpha = 5\%$.

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	42,281	3,550		11,909	,000
Parents attention	,370	,070	,460	5,299	,000
Interest to learn	,364	,096	,443	5,095	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Achievement

Table 4.2 Results of Multiple Regression Analysis Test

The constant (a) value in table 4.10 is known to be 4 2.281 while the value of parental attention (b1) is 0.3 70 and the value of learning interest (b2) is 0 . 364, so the regression equation is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 42.281 + 0.370X_1 + 0.364X_2 + 3076.929$$

1. A constant of 42.281 means that the consistent value of the learning outcome variable is 42.281.
2. The regression coefficient X1 is 0.370 and X2 is 0.364. The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be said that the direction of influence of variable X1 and variable X2 on Y is positive.
3. e is the possible error in the regression equation model which is caused by the possibility of variables that influence the learning outcome variables, but are not found in the regression equation.

t test

The partial test (t) is used to determine whether the hypothesis used is accepted or rejected, with a confidence level of 95% or $\alpha=5\%$, with the following conditions:

1. If $t_{count} > t_{table}$, then the independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable.
2. If $t_{count} < t_{table}$, then the independent variable has no effect on the dependent variable.

Table 4.3 t test results

Model		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	42.281	3.550		11,909	,000
	Parents attention	,370	,070	.460	5.299	.000
	MinatBelajar	.364	.071	.443	5.095	.000

a. Dependent Variable: PrestasiBelajar

Based on table 4. 3 The calculated t value of parental attention (5, 299) is greater than the t table (1.65462), so it can be seen that the study habits variable (X1) rejects the null hypothesis (Ho1) and accepts the alternative hypothesis (Ha1). Furthermore, the calculated t value of learning interest (5.095) is greater than the t table (1.65462), so it can be seen that the learning interest variable (X2) rejects the null hypothesis (Ho2) and accepts the alternative hypothesis (Ha2). Thus it

can be concluded that the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable. This can be seen in the table.

F test

The F test is carried out to find out whether the independent variables together have an influence on the dependent variable. In this case, the calculated F is compared with the F_{table} with the following conditions:

1. If $F_{count} > F_{table}$, then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted
2. If $F_{count} < F_{table}$, then H_1 is rejected and H_0 is rejected.

Table 4.4 F Test Results

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	698,714	2	349,357	17,485	,000 ^b
	Residual	3076.929	154	19,980		
	Total	3775.643	156			
a. Dependent Variable: Learning Achievement						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Parental Attention, Interest in Learning						

Based on table 4.4, the calculated F value (17.485) is greater than the table F value (2.66). This indicates that the research results reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_a). Thus, simultaneously parental attention and student interest in learning influence the student achievement variable at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar with a significant level of influence. This gives meaning to the hypothesis which states that parental attention and student interest in learning simultaneously influence the variable student learning achievement at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar school as acceptable.

Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 4.5 Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,430 ^a	,185	,174	4,470
a. Predictors: (Constant), Parental Attention, Interest in Learning				
b. Dependent Variable: Learning Achievement				

The R Square coefficient of determination value in table 4.10 is known to be 0.185. Which means that 18.5 % of the variables of parental attention and interest in learning influence student achievement at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar. Meanwhile, 81.5% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

DISCUSSION

The research was conducted to determine the influence of learning facilities and learning motivation on the economic learning outcomes of Class XI students at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar. In this research there are 3 problem formulations that need to be answered through the research that has been carried out.

1. The Influence of Learning Facilities and Learning Motivation on Economics Learning Outcomes of Class XI Students at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar

Based on the results of research that has been carried out, the regression coefficient value is 0.370 obtained $t_{\text{table}} 1.65776$. So, it is obtained that $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}}$, namely $5.299 > 1.65462$. So it can be seen that the parental attention variable (X1) rejects the null hypothesis (Ho1) and accepts the alternative hypothesis (Ha1). Which means there is a positive and significant influence between the parental attention variable on Economics Learning Achievement in class X SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar. The regression coefficient value obtained from this research is 0.370, this shows that with every additional 1 score point for the Parental Attention variable, there will be an increase in Learning Achievement of 0.370. On the other hand, if the learning interest score decreases by 1 point, this will be followed by a decrease in learning outcomes of 0.370.

2. The Influence of Learning Motivation on Economic Learning Outcomes of Class XI IPS Students at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar

Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, the regression coefficient value of 0.364 is obtained. The calculated t value of learning motivation (5.095) is greater than the t_{table} (1.65462), so it can be seen that the learning motivation variable (X2) rejects the null hypothesis (Ho2) and accept the alternative hypothesis (Ha2). Thus it can be concluded that the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable. Which means there is a positive and significant influence between the variable Learning Motivation on Economics Learning Results for class X SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar. The regression coefficient value obtained from this research is 0.364, this shows that with every additional 1 score point for the Learning Interest variable, there will be an increase in Learning Achievement of 0.364. On the other hand, if the Parental Attention score decreases by 1 point, this will be followed by a decrease in learning outcomes of 0.364.

3. **The Influence of Learning Facilities and Learning Motivation on Economic Learning Outcomes of Class XI IPS Students at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar.**

To answer the third problem formulation, the influence of parental attention and interest in learning on the economics learning achievement of class XI IPS students can be seen from the results of research that has been carried out as follows:

The independent variables, namely parental attention and interest in learning, simultaneously influence economic learning achievement. This is in accordance with the results of the hypothesis test carried out with the help of SPSS release 24. It was found that the calculated F value (17.485) was greater than the F table value (2.66). This indicates that the research results reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_a). Thus, together parental attention and student interest in learning influence the student learning achievement variable at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar with a significant level of influence. This gives meaning to the hypothesis which states that parental attention and student interest in learning jointly influence the student achievement variable at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar school as acceptable.

Research conducted by Afiatin Nisa with the title: "**The Influence of Parental Attention and Interest in Learning on Social Science Learning Achievement.**" The purpose of this research is to determine the influence of parental attention on student learning achievement, the influence of student interest on student learning achievement. The final step is to find out whether there is a significant influence between parental attention and student interest on student learning achievement. This research was conducted in Class XI of State High Schools around Depok City with a sample of 60 students taken randomly. The method used in the research is a survey. Data on Parental Attention, Student Interest, and Social Studies Learning Achievement were obtained from the test. Data analysis uses descriptive statistical methods, multiple correlation coefficients, coefficients of determination, and multiple regression analysis. To test statistics, the t test and f test are used. The results of data analysis show that there is a significant influence of parental attention and student interest on social studies learning achievement.

Therefore, to be able to improve learning achievement, it is necessary to increase parental attention in learning by increasing it according to indicators. Apart from that, interest in learning also influences students in learning because the enthusiasm and desire to learn comes from a student, so teachers are asked to help students to be enthusiastic in the learning process and produce good learning results.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There are several conclusions made by researchers based on the research results that have been researched and discussed in the previous chapter, namely as follows:

1. There is a positive and significant influence of parental attention on learning achievement. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of parental attention (5.299) > t table value (1.65462) which means this variable is significant.
2. There is a positive and significant influence of interest in learning on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of interest in learning (5.095) > t table value (1.65462) which means this variable is significant.
3. Parental attention and interest in learning together influence learning achievement. This achievement can be seen in the F test where the calculated F value (17.485) > table F value (2.66). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.185, which means that 18.5% of the variables of parental attention and interest in learning influence student achievement at SMA Negeri 3 Pematang Siantar, and the remaining 81.5% is the influence of variables not examined in this research. .

FURTHER STUDY

It is recommended that other researchers who will research the same problem be able to choose research subjects with different characteristics and can research other variables that can influence economic learning achievement besides the variables of parental attention and interest in learning, so that they can further develop knowledge.

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